

A Brief Review at Industrial Construction

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Introduction

Industrialization and the use of modular components in buildings is one of the best methods of mass production in the construction of housing and urban residential spaces. This method has always been used by humans for thousands of years in primitive housing; So that the age of industrialization in the building can be equated with the antiquity of architecture and the beginning of early construction by humans. This method has reached the best possible shape and quality with the advancement of science and technology in the present age and has caused many advances in mass production of buildings (Ghiasvand 2015). Increasing demand for housing due to population growth, migration to cities and finally the development of urbanization on the one hand and the lack of adequate supply of housing due to the inefficiency of traditional construction methods on the other hand, has made the use of building industrialization in different societies impossible (HosseinAlipour 2010). Today, the development of science and technology has led to the emergence of new technologies in the field of construction (Taqdiri 2013). In fact, for the production of quality, cheap and mass housing, other traditional methods of construction do not meet the current demand of society, so improving the quality of materials, design and implementation methods, speeding up the construction process, competition in technological progress, optimal use Labor force and the use of new manufacturing technologies are among the influential components in this industry (Zahraei 2015).

Key words: Housing, building industrialization, new construction technologies, industrialization strategy, construction.

Disadvantages of Building industrialization

In addition to the advantages of prefabricated, the disadvantages of using prefabricated have also been considered. Inflexible to changes in design, high initial cost, lack of related research, time in the early stages of design, little attention to the advantages of using conventional construction methods in the workshop, limited construction workshop space for storage of prefabricated components, sealing problems. When connecting prefabricated components, contractors have little experience, aesthetic uniformity in the building, and low demand for prefabricated components.(Golabchi 2012, Sarja 1998, sarja 2006, staib 2008, vafamehr 2010, warszawski 1999).

Advantages of Building industrialization

<p>COST</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce build time • Optimal use of materials • Mass production • Reduce material waste 	<p>TIME</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce build time • Possibility of serialization • Mechanize production • Modular production 	<p>QUALITY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life of materials • Waste materials • Light weight • the environment • Performance optimization
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Many researchers have pointed out the benefits of using prefabricated. The seven main advantages of using prefabricated to collect data are as follows: Strong design in the early stages of design to better use prefabricated, better monitor the quality of prefabricated products, reduce overall manufacturing costs, Reduction of execution time, better environmental function through reduction of waste, integration of design and execution and aesthetic aspects of the building.(Golabchi 2012, Sarja 1998, sarja 2006, staib 2008, vafamehr 2010, warszawski 1999).

Conclusions

Prefabrication provides suitable solutions to the problem of large-scale waste generation in construction workshops. The use of prefabricated has had many capabilities, including better monitoring of the quality of prefabricated products in the construction industry. However, there are many obstacles to its development and application. Nevertheless, it is possible to achieve environmental and quality standards and reduce construction time costs. To make better use of prefabrication, it is necessary to pay attention to the execution methods from the initial stages of design. Development of effective prefabrication methods for large projects, mass housing, construction of residential and private commercial projects are effective in reducing waste production and the use of prefabrication methods and modular construction should be expanded with awareness of environmental aspects. Prefabrication will only be successful if contractors and stakeholders are aware of the cost reduction. In the following cases, prefabrication will lead to cost savings: the use of mechanized construction process and heavy machinery, the use of standard construction designs, the conversion of manufacturer construction in the construction workshop to the construction components assembly industry, The use of recycled and recyclable materials in prefabricated building components. However, three motivating factors are required to use prefabrication:

- Environmental aspects: When strict environmental laws and regulations are in place, prefabrication will be one of the ways to reduce waste production.
- Construction costs: Providing more effective and alternative construction methods dramatically reduces construction costs and reduces the need for heavy initial capital.
- Incentive facilities: Incentive facilities for large infrastructure built with prefabricated elements will make the use of prefabricated popular.

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